

THE QUALITY OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGE AND THE ORIENTATION OF THE STUDENTS

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Abstract. *In this article, those who are interested in learning English, but who do not have any base for 1 lesson, are given the skill to be able to briefly tell about themselves, using an interesting method in motivation and teaching basic knowledge.*

Key words: *psychology, motivation, certificate, brainstorming, effective.*

КАЧЕСТВО ПРЕПОДАВАНИЯ ИНОСТРАННОГО ЯЗЫКА И НАПРАВЛЕННОСТЬ СТУДЕНТОВ

Аннотация. *В этой статье заинтересованным в изучении английского языка, но не имеющим никакой базы за 1 урок дается навык уметь коротко рассказать о себе, с использованием интересующего метода в мотивации и преподавании начальных знаний.*

Ключевые слова: *психология, мотивация, сертификат, мозговой штурм, эффективность.*

Several areas of knowledge are determined every year in Uzbekistan, the development of which is given priority attention. This year physics and foreign languages have become such areas.

Studying a new language makes students hesitate, moreover in some cases distrust learners themselves due to not learning it from young age. As a matter of fact if a learner have a little background of knowledge, it's enough to go on learning this sphere for themselves. From this point of view teachers face two types of student one is eager to learn, the other doesn't want to study or gives up studying chance at once. But necessity of studying a foreign language getting certificates gives not only foreign language teaching teachers but also if another sphere candidate has this certificate they can also have a great opportunity at work.

In the newspaper "Правда востока On May 6, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev chaired a meeting on measures to improve the system of teaching foreign languages.

"The time has come to create in Uzbekistan a new system of teaching foreign languages, which will become a solid foundation for the future. Since we set ourselves the goal of building a competitive state, from now on, graduates of schools, lyceums, colleges and universities must be fluent in at least two foreign languages. This strict requirement should become the main criterion for the work of the head of each education institution", Shavkat Mirziyoyev.

In general, the main activity of the Agency will be the development and implementation of methods, recommendations and textbooks for all categories of the population along the chain "kindergarten – school – higher education – enterprise".

However we have a system of learning a foreign language from the kindergarten, the teachers of the kindergarten can study a foreign language and also they have chance of getting certificates as "National certificate" as Multilevel, Linguaskill, TESOL, Aptiss which has given a lot of opportunities from the republic

As mentioned in the article studying a language to native speakers from young age develops high quality education in the young generation system, but what about the teachers of other spheres as I'm taking into the consideration "the teachers of the kindergarten" if they get the degrees of

foreign language they can also have the salary better as they get chance of teaching English for instance.

Older students who hasn't opened books for long but nowadays its necessary to get degree certificates the first thing they face is actually brainstorming as "I can't or I cant manage". In fact on terms of work almost every lesson I can see this problem. So in that case how the teachers must interact with them. In this case three types of studying technics can help me as I use in my teaching system

- Psychology "Changing students mind from I cant to I can
- Motivation- enjoy learning
- Teachers must choose the best materials which gives better results "from the easiest to intermediate or advanced"

1. Psychology: teachers must find the weakest and fearing sides of the learner and from the tasks the teacher shows them that it's not difficult

2. Motivation to enjoy learning a language, motivating individually. A good working knowledge of English can radically change somebody's life

3. I think every teacher who is teaching native learner must have their own teaching material as they can manage to develop learning a language as the other's works cant be as effective as your own one. Teachers can use in some cases from other materials but if the teacher works with his own material or guidance it can be more effective. So I'll share with my own work which is practiced and got good results in teaching on the first in the "Innovation Instetute of Nukus" in the faculty of Pre-school (there are only two students who know elementary words in English, some of them work in the kindergarten)

So on the first lesson we have "Introduction" we can ask elementary questions as "What's your name?", "How old are you?", "Who do you live with?". As it was the first lesson only some of them could answer. So as I saw the problem I have read them first the Resolution of getting a degree if they get National certificate how can they get better salary. How can they manage to it as the work shows them in the results. I promised them at end of the lesson they can retell about themselves "10" sentences. And in this position teacher must persuade all the students to attend the lesson in my lesson "Ten sentences" about themselves got interest them. so the first sentence

Almost all students know the meaning of "My name is.." and I changed it to MY full name is...

I am ... years old (here we teach how to count so I promised in two minutes I can teach them to count the first question is "Can you count to ten" they answered yes so the rule is from 13-19 we must add "teen" from 20-90 we add "ty" for example 14- first four then add "teen" as fourteen if we want to say 40 first of all four then add "ty")

This is the first tip that can take their interest to the text as they can orally say their ages and you can see smile on their faces from that they wait what's on.

The third is I write on the blackboard ... "in Nukus" as they guess the meaning of the sentence as live somewhere. "I am from Karakalpakstan. I live in Nukus"

The fourth "I am single/ I am married" at the bottom of this sentence I write one stick to the word single and two sticks to the word married and give chance to them find the meaning. If it's difficult to find an answer we can add a word related "Family". After finding the translation we write these words.

“I am single. I live with my family, parents, siblings and me” – to the place mother and father we will learn parents and the second is siblings on the contrary of brother and sister. So you must write down as Parents =mother and father, siblings=brother and sister. I am married. I have a wife/husband. Two children, a son and a daughter, mother-in=law, father-in law.

This words may be easiest one to them because they can imagine their families and can easily remember. To mother we can add in-law and a new word will become.

I like ... We can ask about their hobbies and in parallel way we can write a translation. In this case they can remember this words as imagining the person who interests to it when they are saying they point out the student who interests to it, but we mustn't require all of the words at once I like listening to music, drawing, riding a horse, playing computer games, sewing, reading a book, watching TV, growing flowers etc.

Here we can ask what about you can add for yourself ? So the next sentence is I work at kindergarten as a teacher or I don't work and the last one is I study at Nukus innovation institute. My future plan is to be a teacher.

These sentences can easily get students interests and make sure at the end of the lesson they can manage retell about themselves. If a learner can use what they have learned it can motivate and on the other lessons you can use other more complicated tasks as you have got their interests. Further we can use video audio lesson educational broadcasts to develop the language.

The quality of teaching shows its results when the students get interest and are on the process of learning. «A child who has mastered a profession and language at school represents a great achievement of our society», Shavkat Mirziyoyev has said.

In conclusion I want to say if a teacher of kindergarten knows a foreign language it can also add better developments in the life of our youth, first of all knowing a foreign language can change not only youths life but also a new learner can make more progress in their profession.

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